

Sterols from *Leucas lanata*

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L*UCAS lanata* Benth^{1,2} (*Labiatae*) is an annual herb scatterly found in Tripura. It has several medicinal uses¹. As a part of our programme to explore the herbs of Tripura, we investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of the plant and isolated five sterols. In this communication, we report the isolation, characterisation and composition of these sterols on the basis of spectral and glc analysis.

The aerial parts of *L. lanata* collected from greater Agartala in September (1985) were air-dried and milled. The milled aerial parts (1 kg) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet for 48 h. The petrol extract was distilled to a small volume and the concentrated extract was evaporated to a gummy residue (3.9 g). The residue (3.8 g) was column chromatographed through silica gel (60–120 mesh). The petrol eluate on evaporation of solvent gave an oily residue which gave positive Salkowski reaction and Liebermann–Burchard test for steroids. The petrol–benzene (1:1) eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a solid residue which was found to be a mixture on tlc. This residue on repeated chromatography gave a crystalline solid (0.025 g), m.p. 143–57° from benzene–chloroform mixture. The crystalline solid gave positive Salkowski reaction and Liebermann–Burchard test for steroids. The solid showed ir absorptions at (KBr) 3400 (OH), 1615 (C=C), 1465, 1380, 1060, 1025, 970 (*trans*-olefinic) and 960 cm⁻¹. The EI-mass spectrum of the solid was more diagnostic to ascertain the nature of the skeletal structure. The spectrum showed significant peaks at *m/z* 414 (36.9 percent), 412 (55.0), 400 (22.8), 399 (15.2), 398 (7.2), 396 (26.0), 394 (15.6), 385 (9.4), 382 (19.9), 381 (20.3), 372 (20.0), 369 (32.3), 367 (18.5), 329 (55.7), 327 (14.9), 314 (81.4), 300 (28.2), 273 (16.7), 271 (33.5), 255 (74.2), 253 (4.2), 231 (29.4), 229 (26.1), 213 (44.6) and 43 (100.0), which can be rationalised³ by considering the solid to be a mixture of β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol, brassicasterol and cholesterol or their C₂₄ epimers. The relative abundance of the mass peaks also suggested that stigmasterol or its epimer be the major component in the mixture. The 100 MHz ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃, TMS as internal standard) of the solid displayed methyl signals at δ 0.68 (s), 0.79 (d), 0.80 (t), 0.85 (d), 1.0 (s), 1.02 (d), methine signal at δ 3.53 (1H, m,

H–3), olefinic signals at δ 5.04 (0.75 H, dd) and 5.12 (0.75 H, dd) for H–22 and H–23, and 5.36 (1H, br s, H–6) further corroborating³ Δ^5 and $\Delta^5, 22$ sterol mixture.

In order to get the composition of the sterol mixture, the solid (0.01 g) was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine and the acetylated product was worked up in the usual manner. The acetylated product (0.005 g), m.p. 121°, ν_{max} 1725 (acetate C=O) cm⁻¹, δ 2.02 (3H, s, OAc), suggested the presence of acetyl function in it. Its EI-mass spectrum showed significant (M–HOAc) peaks at *m/z* 396 (41.0 percent), 394 (100.0), 382 (15.4), 380 (2.6) and 368 (1.0) along with peaks at *m/z* 456 (20.5), 442 (3.8), 379 (5.1), 351 (14.1), 255 (51.3), and 213 (15.4), suggesting it to be a mixture of acetates of sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol, brassicasterol and cholesterol or their C₂₄-epimers. Finally, the acetate mixture was subjected to glc on a Pye–Unicam 104 using 3% OV-17 column and FID detector; operating conditions being: column temperature 260°, injection port and FID temperature 280°, carrier gas N₂ at flow rate 50 ml min⁻¹ and chart speed 160 mm h⁻¹. The approximate composition (by peak area) of the acetate mixture as determined^{4,5} in glc was found to be cholesterol (RR_t 1.00; 2.2%), brassicasterol (1.13; 11.9); campesterol (1.31; 13.1), stigmasterol (1.42; 55.6) and β -sitosterol (1.61; 17.2). This composition may be changed as the C₂₄ epimers of the said sterols having the same RR_t values.

The oily residue (0.05 g) obtained from the petrol eluate of the main column was saponified in the usual manner and the non-saponified part (0.01 g) was chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol–benzene (1:3) eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a residue, which on crystallisation from benzene–chloroform mixture afforded colourless crystals (0.003 g), m.p. 80–90°. It gave positive tests for steroids. It was acetylated and acetylated product, m.p. 53°, was subjected to glc as above. Glc revealed the approximate composition of the acetylated product as acetate of cholesterol (24.0%), brassicasterol (4.0), campesterol (15.6), stigmasterol (27.6), β -sitosterol (19.2) and an unidentified sterol (RR_t 1.69 with respect to cholesteryl acetate, 9.6%).

The foregoing results suggest that sterols may be present in plants both in the free state as well as esters and their relative abundance depends on the requirement of plant biosystem.

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Electroreduction and Coulometric Determination of Europium(III) in Calcium Nitrate Tetrahydrate Melt

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It is possible to acquire more information regarding the chemical behaviour of metal ions by changing over from aqueous to non-aqueous or molten salt media. Such information can be acquired in general by applying electrochemical techniques. In recent years, an array of electrochemical methods such as coulometry, amperometry and variations thereof are available to the chemist. Amongst the metal ions the rare earths are less explored.

Europium is unique amongst the rare earths due to its suitable thermal neutron cross-section of 43 000 barn; due to which it is increasingly used at control rod material. Hence, its analytical estimation is also important. Earlier works on europium in non-aqueous¹⁻⁴ and molten salt media^{5,6} have shown that there is need of further work for better understanding of the lower oxidation states.

Much of the work in molten salts is done in eutectic mixtures of alkali metal salts at ~150–250°. The hydrated metal nitrates also melt over fairly low range of temperatures and hence, we have studied the electrochemistry of reduction of rare earth ions in molten hydrated metal nitrates. This paper presents the study of electroreduction and coulometric generation of europous ions in calcium

nitrate tetrahydrate melt, and subsequent biampereometric titration with dichromate ions at 55°. Simultaneous determination of europium and samarium has also been studied.

Experimental

For polarographic studies a Sargent-Welch XVI recording polarograph was used along with a dropping mercury electrode ($m=19 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ $t=3 \text{ s}$, $h=60 \text{ cm}$, $A=0.1072 \text{ cm}^2$). For coulometric generation of europous ion a Systronics 621 stabilised DC power supply which gave ripple-free current, was used. A dead-stop titrator fabricated in our laboratory, was used for biampereometric measurements. A jacketed burette and jacketed cells were used in all experiments; constant temperature ($55 \pm 1^\circ$) was maintained by circulation of water from Adept water thermostat. A double walled, water-jacketted borosilicate glass cell was used for polarographic measurements. A double walled, water-jacketted borosilicate glass cell (Fig 1) was used for both coulometric generation and biampereometric titration. The generating electrodes were

Fig. 1. Coulometric assembly.

of platinum. The anode was placed in a fritted glass compartment, whereas the cathode was in the outer compartment. Two indicator electrodes of platinum wire, were used in the biampereometric end-point detection. An externally driven stirrer was used for proper stirring of the viscous calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt.

Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate and potassium dichromate were of A.R. grade, and europium nitrate was prepared from europium oxide (Indian Rare Earths) by dissolution in 4 M nitric acid and by slow evaporation.